

The Halsey isotherm for water contaminant adsorption is fake

Khim Hoong Chu ^{a,*}, Hadis Bashiri ^b, Mohd Ali Hashim ^a, Mohd Yunus Abd Shukor ^c, Jean-Claude Bollinger ^d

^a Department of Chemical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, University of Malaya, Kuala Lumpur 50603, Malaysia

^b Department of Physical Chemistry, Faculty of Chemistry, University of Kashan, Kashan, Iran

^c Department of Biochemistry, Faculty of Biotechnology and Biomolecular Sciences, Universiti Putra Malaysia, Agriculture Innovation Life, Serdang 43400, Selangor, Malaysia

^d Université de Limoges, Laboratoire E2Lim, Faculté des Sciences & Techniques, 87060 Limoges, France

* Corresponding author.

Email address: khimchu@gmail.com (K.H. Chu)

Abstract

We present a critique of the Halsey isotherm model (also known as Frenkel–Halsey–Hill), which is used by many researchers to interpret water contaminant adsorption data. We first convert the original Halsey isotherm for gas-phase adsorption to a form appropriate for liquid-phase adsorption. We call this version the “genuine Halsey isotherm.” We then show that the Halsey isotherm currently used in water contaminant adsorption research bears only a partial resemblance to the genuine Halsey isotherm. As such, we label the former the “fake Halsey isotherm.” We go on to prove that the fake Halsey isotherm is mathematically equivalent to the

Freundlich isotherm. Consequently, the modeling results obtained by the fake Halsey isotherm reported in numerous previously published studies have been mostly misleading. Many such reports can be found across a broad spectrum of major journals. Finally, we highlight the data-fitting attributes of the genuine Halsey isotherm. It is shown to be capable of describing adsorption isotherms having types I, II, and III curve shapes.

Keywords: Frenkel–Halsey–Hill; Isotherm misuse; Sigmoid isotherm; Type I isotherm; Type II isotherm; Type III isotherm

1. Introduction

In water contaminant adsorption research, the study of adsorption equilibria is useful for process design or adsorbent development. Theoretical or empirical models are invariably used to summarize the adsorption trends exhibited by the measured data, usually gathered from simple batch experiments. Several well-known models, such as the more than century-old Freundlich and Langmuir equations, are commonly used to correlate favorable or type I isotherms. Many recent studies have tested some lesser-known models, of which a relatively simple one is that proposed by Halsey.

In 1948, Halsey developed a simple analytic isotherm equation for multilayer adsorption of gases [1]. It is also known as the Frenkel–Halsey–Hill (FHH) isotherm in the gas adsorption literature. Since the mid-2000s, the Halsey or FHH isotherm has been used to correlate the adsorption isotherms of many water contaminants, ranging from toxic metals to organic compounds. A sizeable body of work featuring the Halsey isotherm has been published across a broad spectrum of scholarly journals. Quite a large fraction of these reports can be found in several major journals (e.g., *Chemical Engineering Journal* [2–12], *Journal of Hazardous Materials* [13–21], *Separation and Purification Technology* [22–28], and *Journal*

of *Environmental Chemical Engineering* [29–40]). Table 1 presents some representative examples.

Table 1. Examples of water contaminant adsorption data modeled by the Halsey isotherm.

Journal	Ref.	Adsorption system
Chem. Eng. J.	Varala et al. [11]	Zr(IV)/biosorbent
J. Hazard. Mater.	Zhang et al. [12]	Pb(II), Cd(II), Ni(II)/biochar composites
	Goyal et al. [19]	Daidzein, coumestrol/nanozeolite beta
Sep. Purif. Technol.	Nassar et al. [21]	Petroleum pollutants/rice straw
	Kheradmand et al. [27]	Rifampin/nanocomposite
J. Environ. Chem. Eng.	Zhang et al. [28]	Uranium/boron nitride
	Rathi et al. [39]	Fipronil/zeolites
	Aniagor et al. [40]	Fe(II)/modified cellulose

The primary intent of this paper is to show that the use of the Halsey isotherm in water contaminant adsorption research is based on misconceptions. We first demonstrate that the Halsey isotherm as used in water contaminant adsorption research [2–40] bears only a partial resemblance to the original Halsey isotherm. We go on to reveal that the mathematical form of the Halsey isotherm for water contaminant adsorption [2–40] is analogous to that of the famous Freundlich isotherm. As such, in this work, this particular form of the Halsey isotherm is referred to as the “fake Halsey isotherm.” The secondary aim is to highlight the data-fitting attributes of the genuine Halsey isotherm. It is shown to be capable of correlating types I, II, and III isotherm data.

2. The original and fake Halsey isotherms

2.1. The original Halsey isotherm

The Halsey isotherm for multilayer adsorption of gases [1] is usually written in the form of Eq. (1), where θ is the surface coverage at the relative pressure p/p_0 (p and p_0 are the equilibrium and saturation pressures), and k and n are characteristic constants for the given adsorption system and temperature.

$$\ln\left(\frac{p}{p_0}\right) = -\frac{k}{\theta^n} \quad (1)$$

2.2. The fake Halsey isotherm

The Halsey isotherm commonly used to correlate water contaminant adsorption data by means of linear regression is given by Eq. (2). In this linearized expression, q is the adsorbed-phase concentration, c is the liquid-phase concentration at equilibrium, and k and n are fitting parameters. Rearranging Eq. (2) yields Eq. (3), which is nonlinear in the two fitting parameters. Eq. (3) may be fitted to experimental data by means of nonlinear regression, but it is rarely used in water contaminant adsorption research.

$$\ln(q) = \frac{1}{n}\ln(k) - \frac{1}{n}\ln(c) \quad (2)$$

$$q = \left(\frac{k}{c}\right)^{1/n} \quad (3)$$

In addition to Eq. (2), other linearized Halsey isotherms have been reported in the literature of water contaminant adsorption. For example, Eqs. (4) [41–47] and (5) [7,35,48–53] have been used to correlate water contaminant isotherm data. These two equations are, of course, equivalent to each other.

$$\ln(q) = \frac{1}{n}\ln(k) - \frac{1}{n}\ln\left(\frac{1}{c}\right) \quad (4)$$

$$\ln(q) = \frac{1}{n}\ln(k) + \frac{1}{n}\ln(c) \quad (5)$$

The focus here is on Eq. (2), which is far more popular than Eqs. (4) and (5). We assert that Eq. (2) is a bogus version of the original Halsey isotherm because it bears limited resemblance to the original form given by Eq. (1). As such, we label Eq. (2) the “fake Halsey isotherm.” Justification for our assertion and the equation label is given below.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Comparison of Eqs. (1) and (2)

Here we convert the Halsey isotherm for gas-phase adsorption [Eq. (1)] to a form appropriate for use in liquid-phase adsorption research and compare the resulting expression to Eq. (2). Eq. (1) can be extended to liquid-phase adsorption by replacing the equilibrium and saturation pressures, p and p_0 , in Eq. (1) with the equilibrium concentration c and the solute solubility c_s , respectively. The surface coverage θ in Eq. (1) is replaced by q/q_m , where q_m is the adsorbed-phase concentration corresponding to a complete monolayer. Accordingly, the Halsey isotherm for liquid-phase adsorption is given by Eq. (6).

$$\ln\left(\frac{c}{c_s}\right) = -\frac{k}{(q/q_m)^n} \quad (6)$$

If the solubility c_s is infinite or unknown, it is usually treated as an empirical parameter. For such cases, Eq. (6) is rewritten as Eq. (7), where α is a constant of proportionality ($\alpha = 1/c_s$), expressed in units of the reciprocal of the liquid-phase concentration.

$$\ln(\alpha c) = -\frac{k}{(q/q_m)^n} \quad (7)$$

There are four unknown parameters in Eq. (7): α , q_m , k , and n . It is possible to reduce the number of unknown parameters to three by combining q_m and k into a single entity. By letting $\beta = (k)(q_m^n)$, Eq. (7) is transformed into Eq. (8), which has three unknown parameters: α , β , and n .

$$\ln(\alpha c) = -\frac{\beta}{q^n} \quad (8)$$

Rearranging Eq. (8) yields Eq. (9). Given that Eq. (9) has three unknown parameters, nifty mathematical tricks are needed to determine all three parameters by linear regression.

$$\ln(q) = \frac{1}{n}\ln(\beta) - \frac{1}{n}\ln\left[\ln\left(\frac{1}{\alpha c}\right)\right] \quad (9)$$

If the solubility c_s is available, Eq. (9) is rewritten as Eq. (10), which has two unknown parameters. If the data follows Eq. (10), a plot of $\ln(q)$ versus $\ln(c_s/c)$ should yield a straight line.

$$\ln(q) = \frac{1}{n} \ln(\beta) - \frac{1}{n} \ln \left[\ln \left(\frac{c_s}{c} \right) \right] \quad (10)$$

By comparing Eq. (2) and Eq. (9) or (10), it should be apparent to the reader that the former shows only a partial resemblance to the latter. Henceforth, Eq. (2) is referred to as the “fake Halsey isotherm,” while Eq. (8) is called the “genuine Halsey isotherm” for water contaminant adsorption. Alarming, the fake Halsey isotherm can be found in several review articles [15,20,24,54–57], which tend to attract a wide audience of readers, especially early-career researchers.

3.2. Origin of the fake Halsey isotherm

The analysis presented in Section 3.1 motivates the following question: What is the original source of the fake Halsey isotherm defined by Eq. (2)? Based on our investigation, the origin of Eq. (2) can be traced to a 2006 paper published by Başar [13]. This paper has been cited by many subsequent studies that used Eq. (2) in data fitting. Although Halsey’s 1948 paper was cited in the work of Başar [13], mistakes were made in interpreting the original Halsey isotherm.

Interestingly, a 2004 paper by Gürses et al. [58] put forward a version of the Halsey isotherm for liquid-phase adsorption that differs from Eq. (2), as shown in Eq. (11). Rearranging Eq. (11) yields Eq. (12), which is nonlinear in the fitting parameters. Although Eq. (11) has attracted little attention, its mathematical form is very similar to that of the genuine Halsey isotherm defined by Eq. (9). A conspicuous difference between the two expressions is that Eq. (11) is missing the α -term of Eq. (9).

$$\ln(q) = \frac{1}{n} \ln(k) - \frac{1}{n} \ln \left[\ln \left(\frac{1}{c} \right) \right] \quad (11)$$

$$q = \left[\frac{k}{\ln(1/c)} \right]^{1/n} \quad (12)$$

3.3. Equivalence of the fake Halsey isotherm and the Freundlich isotherm

Many studies have compared the data-fitting abilities of the fake Halsey isotherm and the Freundlich isotherm. We assert that such comparisons are meaningless because the two isotherm equations are mathematically equivalent. As such, they must provide exactly the same fit to a given set of isotherm data.

To support our assertion, here we compare the fake Halsey isotherm and the Freundlich isotherm by fitting the two equations to the same set of isotherm data taken from the literature of water contaminant adsorption. To minimize the risk of spurious fitting in regression analyses, two previously published isotherm data sets [3,14] with multiple data points (10 or more) were selected as case studies. In the original studies, the data set reported by Oubagaranadin et al. [14] was analyzed using the linearized Halsey isotherm given by Eq. (2), while that reported by Hadi et al. [3] was modeled using a nonlinear version of Eq. (2). In this work, all linear and nonlinear regression analyses were carried out using the commercial software GraphPad Prism version 9 for Windows.

3.3.1. Case 1: mercury adsorption by activated carbon

The first data set, taken from the work of Oubagaranadin et al. [14], describes the adsorption of mercury by an activated carbon adsorbent. The authors used seven isotherm models to correlate the experimental mercury isotherm, including the fake Halsey isotherm [Eq. (2)]. The parameter estimates obtained by the fake Halsey isotherm, taken from the original study [14], are presented in Table 2, column 3. To verify the reported parameter estimates, Eq. (2) was fitted to the mercury isotherm data characterized by 10 data points, as shown in Fig. 1A. The resulting parameter estimates are given in Table 2, column 4. As seen in Table 2, our estimates for n and k agree closely with the reported values. The two parameter estimates

obtained in this work are used to plot the q versus c curve shown in Fig. 1B, calculated from Eq. (3). It is evident that the calculated curve can track the favorable or type I isotherm without an apparent plateau very well.

Table 2. Parameter estimates obtained by fitting the fake Halsey isotherm [Eq. (2)] and the Freundlich isotherm [Eq. (13)] to mercury adsorption data [14].

Isotherm	Parameter	Original study [14]	Present study
Fake Halsey	n	-2.05	-2.06
	k (mg L ⁻¹)(mg g ⁻¹) ^{n}	8.08×10^{-3}	7.58×10^{-3}
Freundlich	m		2.06
	b (mg g ⁻¹)(L mg ⁻¹) ^{1/m}		10.70

Fig. 1. (A) Linear fit of the fake Halsey isotherm [Eq. (2)] to mercury adsorption data [14]. (B) Comparison of mercury adsorption data and q versus c curve calculated from the fake Halsey isotherm [Eq. (3)] using the linear regression-generated parameters of this work.

Fitting Eq. (2) to isotherm data by linear regression is a straightforward data analysis exercise, but, to our surprise, erroneous estimates of the two isotherm parameters n and k are not difficult to find in the literature of water contaminant adsorption. Examples of such faulty parameter estimates are given in the Supplementary Material accompanying this publication.

It is thus important to verify the published values of n and k before they are used for further analysis.

Next, the linearized Freundlich isotherm given by Eq. (13) was fitted to the mercury adsorption data. In Eq. (13), b and m are fitting parameters. The linear fit is shown in Fig. 2A, while the resulting parameter estimates are presented in Table 2, column 4. The linear fit in Fig. 2A seems to be similar to that in Fig. 1A. In fact, this similarity is expected because the mercury adsorption data are plotted in the form of $\ln(q)$ versus $\ln(c)$ in both figures. Fig. 2B displays the q versus c curve calculated from Eq. (14) using the linear regression-generated parameter estimates. Eq. (14) is, of course, a simple manipulation of Eq. (13). Again, the calculated curve in Fig. 2B is very similar to that in Fig. 1B.

$$\ln(q) = \ln(b) + \frac{1}{m} \ln(c) \quad (13)$$

$$q = bc^{1/m} \quad (14)$$

Fig. 2. (A) Linear fit of the Freundlich isotherm [Eq. (13)] to mercury adsorption data [14]. (B) Comparison of mercury adsorption data and q versus c curve calculated from the Freundlich isotherm [Eq. (14)] using the linear regression-generated parameters given in Table 2.

The similarity of the isotherm curves plotted in Figs. 1 and 2 strongly suggests that the fake Halsey isotherm and the Freundlich isotherm are analogous. This means that the parameters of the fake Halsey isotherm are related to those of the Freundlich isotherm. A comparison of Eqs. (3) and (14) gives Eqs. (15) and (16), which define the relationships between the parameters of the two isotherms. Eqs. (15) and (16) allow one to calculate the values of the Halsey parameters n and k by using the fitted values of the Freundlich parameters m and b or vice versa.

$$n = -m \quad (15)$$

$$k = b^n = b^{-m} \quad (16)$$

Using the values of b and m given in Table 2, Eq. (15) gives $n = -m = -2.06$, while Eq. (16) yields $k = b^{-m} = (10.7)^{-2.06} = 7.58 \times 10^{-3} (\text{mg L}^{-1})(\text{mg g}^{-1})^n$. These calculated values of n and k are identical to the fitted values of n and k given in Table 2, column 4. This means that it is not necessary to fit the fake Halsey isotherm to experimental data in order to determine its two unknown parameters. They can be estimated by plugging the fitted values of the Freundlich parameters into Eqs. (15) and (16). The results of this case study support our assertion that the fake Halsey isotherm given by Eq. (2) is analogous to the Freundlich isotherm given by Eq. (13). It follows that Eq. (3) is equivalent to Eq. (14). The fake Halsey isotherm is actually the Freundlich isotherm in disguise.

3.3.2. Case 2: dye adsorption by activated carbon

The second data set, taken from the work of Hadi et al. [3], describes the adsorption of the dye acid blue 113 by an activated carbon adsorbent derived from pine cones. Seven isotherm models, including the fake Halsey isotherm, were used to correlate the experimental data. Fig. 3 displays the experimental dye isotherm characterized by 11 data points. Hadi et al. [3] used a nonlinear version of the fake Halsey isotherm [Eq. (2)] to interpret the dye adsorption data, given here by Eq. (17), which is a simple rearrangement of Eq. (2). Because Eq. (17) is

nonlinear in the two fitting parameters, it was fitted to the dye adsorption data by nonlinear regression. The parameter estimates reported in the original study are reproduced in Table 3, column 3. It should be noted that a zero value was reported for the parameter k .

$$q = \exp\left[\frac{1}{n} \ln(k) - \frac{1}{n} \ln(c)\right] \quad (17)$$

Fig. 3. (A) Nonlinear fit of the fake Halsey isotherm [Eq. (3)] to acid blue 113 adsorption data [3]. (B) Nonlinear fit of the Freundlich isotherm [Eq. (14)] to acid blue 113 adsorption data.

Table 3. Parameter estimates obtained by fitting the fake Halsey isotherm (Eq. (17) in the original study and Eq. (3) in the present study) and the Freundlich isotherm [Eq. (14)] to acid blue 113 adsorption data [3].

Isotherm	Parameter	Original study [3]	Present study
Fake Halsey	n	-5.74	-5.61
	$k \text{ (mg L}^{-1}\text{)(mg g}^{-1}\text{)}^n$	0.0	2.01×10^{-12}
Freundlich	m		5.61
	$b \text{ (mg g}^{-1}\text{)(L mg}^{-1}\text{)}^{1/m}$		122.0

The nonlinear Halsey isotherm used by Hadi et al. [3], Eq. (17), can be further simplified to the form given by Eq. (3). Here, Eq. (3) was fitted to the dye adsorption data by nonlinear regression. The nonlinear Halsey fit, shown in Fig. 3A, was calculated using the resulting parameter estimates given in Table 3, column 4. Eq. (3) can track the experimental

data fairly well, as can be seen in Fig. 3A. Table 3 shows that our estimate for n agrees with the corresponding estimate reported in the original study. The estimate for k obtained by the nonlinear fit of Eq. (3) is very small (see Table 3), contrasting the zero value for k produced by the nonlinear fit of Eq. (17) in the original study. It seems that the mathematical form of Eq. (3) may have an advantage over that of Eq. (17) in data correlation. Note that Eq. (3) cannot accept a zero value for k .

For comparison, the nonlinear Freundlich isotherm given by Eq. (14) was fitted to the dye adsorption data, as shown in Fig. 3B. The Freundlich fitted curve in Fig. 3B is practically identical to the Halsey fitted curve in Fig. 3A. Plugging the Freundlich parameter estimates given in Table 3 into Eqs. (15) and (16) gives us the two parameters of the fake Halsey isotherm. According to Eq. (15), $n = -m = -5.61$, which is identical to the fitted value of n obtained by the fake Halsey isotherm. Eq. (16) gives $k = b^{-m} = (122)^{-5.61} = 1.97 \times 10^{-12} (\text{mg L}^{-1})(\text{mg g}^{-1})^n$, which is very similar to the fitted value of k obtained by the fake Halsey isotherm. These modeling results confirm that the fake Halsey isotherm given by Eq. (3) is analogous to the Freundlich isotherm given by Eq. (14). The modeling results of Cases 1–2 back up our claim that the fake Halsey isotherm behaves exactly like the Freundlich isotherm in data correlation. Therefore, comparing the data-fitting abilities of the fake Halsey isotherm and the Freundlich isotherm is a meaningless curve-fitting exercise.

3.4. Data-fitting attributes of the genuine Halsey isotherm

We shall now turn to an analysis of the data-fitting attributes of the genuine Halsey isotherm represented by Eq. (8), which can be written in the form of Eq. (18). In the gas adsorption literature, the original Halsey isotherm [Eq. (1)] has been mostly used to interpret multilayer adsorption, which is known to exhibit a sigmoid or type II isotherm shape. The genuine Halsey isotherm [Eq. (18)] has not been used much to describe liquid-phase type II isotherms, which are typically interpreted using the BET equation and its variants [59,60].

$$q = \left[\frac{\beta}{\ln(1/\alpha c)} \right]^{1/n} \quad (18)$$

Fig. 4 shows the fits of Eq. (18) to two liquid-phase isotherms having type II curve shapes. The Fig. 4A isotherm depicts the adsorption of the dye reactive blue 5G on an orange bagasse biosorbent at 40 °C, taken from the work of Fiorentin et al. [61]. The Fig. 4B isotherm, taken from the work of Lan et al. [62], illustrates the adsorption of antimony on a ferrate adsorbent. The overall sigmoid shapes of the two experimental isotherms are well tracked by Eq. (18). The parameter estimates used to calculate the two fitted curves in Fig. 4 are given in Table 4 (first and second row entries).

Fig. 4. (A) Nonlinear fit of the genuine Halsey isotherm [Eq. (18)] to reactive blue 5G adsorption data [61]. (B) Nonlinear fit of the genuine Halsey isotherm [Eq. (18)] to antimony adsorption data [62].

Table 4. Parameter estimates obtained by fitting the genuine Halsey isotherm [Eq. (18)] to literature adsorption data.

Adsorption system	α (L mg ⁻¹)	β (mg g ⁻¹) ⁿ	n	R^2
Reactive blue 5G/orange bagasse [61]	0.0075	2922	2.26	0.970
Antimony/ferrate [62]	10.78	49.36	1.57	0.964
Phenol/activated carbon [63]	–	3596	1.25	0.831
4-nitrophenol/composite geomaterial [64]	–	7.37	0.039	0.976

Besides type II isotherms, the genuine Halsey isotherm is capable of describing types I and III isotherms. As an example, Eq. (18) was fitted to an experimental isotherm for phenol adsorption on an activated carbon adsorbent at 20 °C, reported by Otero et al. [63]. However, although the nonlinear fit was able to track the hyperbolic data trend, the final parameter estimates were sensitive to the initial values of the parameters used in the nonlinear regression procedure. This parameter estimation problem was solved by reducing the number of adjustable parameters from three to two. The solubility of phenol at 20 °C ($c_s = 83 \text{ g L}^{-1}$) was used to fix the value of α in Eq. (18), which is equal to $1/c_s$. The remaining two adjustable parameters were estimated by fitting Eq. (18) to the phenol isotherm, as shown in Fig. 5A. The fitted curve, calculated using the parameter estimates given in Table 4 (third row entry), agrees fairly well with the experimental phenol isotherm.

Fig. 5. (A) Nonlinear fit of the genuine Halsey isotherm [Eq. (18)] to phenol adsorption data [63]. (B) Nonlinear fit of the genuine Halsey isotherm [Eq. (18)] to 4-nitrophenol adsorption data [64].

The same fitting procedure was applied to a type III isotherm taken from the work of Hamidouche et al. [64]. Fig. 5B displays the experimental isotherm for 4-nitrophenol adsorption on a composite geomaterial at pH 7 and 20 °C. Eq. (18) was fitted to the 4-

nitrophenol isotherm using the solubility of 4-nitrophenol at 20 °C ($c_s = 11.6 \text{ g L}^{-1}$) for α , and the resulting parameter estimates are listed in Table 4 (fourth row entry). Fig. 5B shows that the fitted curve manifests good agreement with the type III isotherm.

In summary, the genuine Halsey isotherm defined by Eq. (18) is a versatile isotherm model capable of describing experimental isotherms having types I, II, and III curve shapes. This data-fitting ability is largely due to the fact that the sigmoid curve predicted by the genuine Halsey isotherm has a floating or variable inflection point. The sigmoid (type II) curve is made up of a convex upward part (type I) and a concave upward part (type III), which are separated by the inflection point. To determine the location of the inflection point, Eq. (18) is differentiated twice with respect to c , as shown in Eq. (19). By setting the second derivative to zero and solving for c , we obtain Eq. (20). Substituting Eq. (20) into Eq. (18) yields Eq. (21). According to Eqs. (20) and (21), the location of the inflection point is a function of the three fitting parameters (α , β , and n).

$$\frac{\partial^2 q}{\partial c^2} = \sqrt[n]{\frac{\beta}{\ln(1/\alpha c)} \frac{1+n-n\ln(1/\alpha c)}{c^2 n^2 \ln^2(1/\alpha c)}} \quad (19)$$

$$c = \frac{1}{\alpha} \frac{1}{\exp(1+1/n)} \quad (20)$$

$$q = \left(\beta \frac{n}{1+n} \right)^{1/n} \quad (21)$$

The inflection point locations for the predicted isotherm curves in Figs. 4 and 5 can now be calculated using Eqs. (20) and (21) and the fitted and assigned values of α , β , and n . The calculated inflection point locations for the four predicted isotherm curves are shown in Fig. 6. For the type II (sigmoid) isotherm curves shown in Figs. 6A and 6B, both the convex upward (type I) and concave upward (type III) parts are visible, separated by the respective inflection points. For the type I isotherm curve depicted in Fig. 6C, the location of the inflection point has been moved far away from the origin, making the concave upward (type III) part no

longer visible. For the type III isotherm curve illustrated in Fig. 6D, the location of the inflection point has been shifted to the origin, effectively eliminating the convex upward (type I) part. Moving the inflection point to different locations on the x -axis therefore allows Eq. (18) to predict type I, II, and III isotherm curves.

Fig. 6. Inflection point locations for the predicted Halsey isotherm curves depicted in Figs. 4A (A), 4B (B), 5A (C), and 5B (D).

4. Conclusions

The original Halsey isotherm for gas-phase adsorption has been converted to a form appropriate for use in liquid-phase adsorption research. This version of the Halsey isotherm, given by Eq. (18), is called the “genuine Halsey isotherm.” It contains three fitting parameters and reduces to a two-parameter expression if the solute solubility is known. The genuine Halsey isotherm is shown to be capable of correlating types I, II, and III adsorption data. The Halsey isotherm currently used in water contaminant adsorption research, given by Eq. (2), is referred to as the “fake Halsey isotherm” because it shows only a partial resemblance to the genuine

Halsey isotherm. The modeling results presented in this work support our assertion that the fake Halsey isotherm and the Freundlich isotherm are one and the same. As such, the two isotherm equations must provide exactly the same fit to a given set of isotherm data. To avoid publishing misleading and meaningless research, modelers are advised to refrain from comparing the data-fitting abilities of the fake Halsey isotherm and the Freundlich isotherm.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no competing financial interests.

References

- [1] G. Halsey, Physical adsorption on non-uniform surfaces, *J. Chem. Phys.* 16 (1948) 931–937, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1746689>.
- [2] Y. Khambhaty, K. Mody, S. Basha, B. Jha, Kinetics, equilibrium and thermodynamic studies on biosorption of hexavalent chromium by dead fungal biomass of marine *Aspergillus niger*, *Chem. Eng. J.* 145 (2009) 489–495, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2008.05.002>.
- [3] M. Hadi, M.R. Samarghandi, G. McKay, Equilibrium two-parameter isotherms of acid dyes sorption by activated carbons: study of residual errors, *Chem. Eng. J.* 160 (2010) 408–416, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2010.03.016>.
- [4] H. Eroglu, E. Varoglu, S. Yapıcı, A. Sahin, An environmentally friendly batch bioadsorption study of the radionuclides ^{67}Ga from aqueous solutions by fibrous tea waste, *Chem. Eng. J.* 165 (2010) 563–572, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2010.09.074>.
- [5] S. Kushwaha, B. Sreedhar, P.P. Sudhakar, Adsorption of Hg^{2+} onto *Borassus Flabellifer*: a redox mechanism, *Chem. Eng. J.* 193–194 (2012) 328–338, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2012.04.050>.

- [6] M.A.A. Aslani, S. Yusan, N. Yenil, S. Kuzu, Sorption profile of uranium (VI) from aqueous medium onto 3-*O*-acetyl-(*S*)-1,2-*O*-trichloroethylidene-5,6,8-trideoxy- α -D-xylo-oct-5(*E*)-eno-1,4-furano-7-ulose (OASOTCETDOXDXOEEFU), Chem. Eng. J. 200–202 (2012) 391–398, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2012.06.072>.
- [7] M.Z. Momčilović, M.S. Randelović, A.R. Zarubica, A.E. Onjia, M. Kokunešoski, B.Z. Matović, SBA-15 templated mesoporous carbons for 2, 4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid removal, Chem. Eng. J. 220 (2013) 276–283, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2012.12.024>.
- [8] M.H. Dehghani, M.M. Taher, A.K. Bajpai, B. Heibati, I. Tyagi, M. Asif, S. Agarwal, V.K. Gupta, Removal of noxious Cr (VI) ions using single-walled carbon nanotubes and multi-walled carbon nanotubes, Chem. Eng. J. 279 (2015) 344–352, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2015.04.151>.
- [9] N.A. Oladoja, Y. Liu, J.E. Drewes, B. Helmreich, Preparation and characterization of a reactive filter for groundwater defluoridation, Chem. Eng. J. 283 (2016) 1154–1167, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2015.08.059>.
- [10] D. Robati, B. Mirza, M. Rajabi, O. Moradi, I. Tyagi, S. Agarwal, V.K. Gupta, Removal of hazardous dyes-BR 12 and methyl orange using graphene oxide as an adsorbent from aqueous phase, Chem. Eng. J. 284 (2016) 687–97, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2015.08.131>.
- [11] S. Varala, B. Dharanija, B. Satyavathi, V.B. Rao, R. Parthasarathy, New biosorbent based on deoiled karanja seed cake in biosorption studies of Zr(IV): optimization using Box–Behnken method in response surface methodology with desirability approach, Chem. Eng. J. 302 (2016) 786–800, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2016.05.088>.
- [12] H. Zhang, H. Yang, J. Shao, Y. Chen, S. Zhang, H. Chen, Multifunctional carboxymethyl cellulose sodium encapsulated phosphorus-enriched biochar composites: multistage

- adsorption of heavy metals and controllable release of soil fertilization, *Chem. Eng. J.* 453 (2023) 139809, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2022.139809>.
- [13] C.A. Başar, Applicability of the various adsorption models of three dyes adsorption onto activated carbon prepared waste apricot, *J. Hazard. Mater.* 135 (2006) 232–241, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2005.11.055>.
- [14] J.U.K. Oubagaranadin, N. Sathyamurthy, Z.V.P. Murthy, Evaluation of Fuller's earth for the adsorption of mercury from aqueous solutions: a comparative study with activated carbon, *J. Hazard. Mater.* 142 (2007) 165–174. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2006.08.001>.
- [15] J. Febrianto, A.N. Kosasih, J. Sunarso, Y.H. Ju, N. Indraswati, S. Ismadji, Equilibrium and kinetic studies in adsorption of heavy metals using biosorbent: a summary of recent studies, *J. Hazard Mater.* 162 (2009) 616–645, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2008.06.042>.
- [16] H.M.H. Gad, A.A. El-Sayed, Activated carbon from agricultural by-products for the removal of Rhodamine-B from aqueous solution, *J. Hazard. Mater.* 168 (2009) 1070–1081, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2009.02.155>.
- [17] D. Das, N. Das, L. Mathew, Kinetics, equilibrium and thermodynamic studies on biosorption of Ag(I) from aqueous solution by macrofungus *Pleurotus platypus*, *J. Hazard. Mater.* 184 (2010) 765–774, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2010.08.105>.
- [18] J. Anandkumar, B. Mandal, Adsorption of chromium(VI) and Rhodamine B by surface modified tannery waste: kinetic, mechanistic and thermodynamic studies, *J. Hazard. Mater.* 186 (2011) 1088–1096, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2010.11.104>.
- [19] N. Goyal, V.K. Bulasara, S. Barman, S., Removal of emerging contaminants daidzein and coumestrol from water by nanozeolite beta modified with tetrasubstituted

- ammonium cation, *J. Hazard. Mater.* 344 (2018) 417–430, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2017.10.051>.
- [20] M.A. Al-Ghouti, D.A. Da'ana, Guidelines for the use and interpretation of adsorption isotherm models: a review, *J. Hazard. Mater.* 393 (2020) 122383, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2020.122383>.
- [21] H.N. Nassar, W.I.M. El-azab, N.Sh. El-Gendy, Sustainable ecofriendly recruitment of bioethanol fermentation lignocellulosic spent waste biomass for the safe reuse and discharge of petroleum production produced water via biosorption and solid biofuel production, *J. Hazard. Mater.* 422 (2022) 126845, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2021.126845>.
- [22] N.A. Oladoja, M.L. Seifert, J.E. Drewes, B. Helmreich, Influence of organic load on the defluoridation efficiency of nano-magnesium oxide in groundwater, *Sep. Purif. Technol.* 174 (2017) 116-125, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2016.10.006>.
- [23] T. Kameda, K. Horikoshi, S. Kumagai, Y. Saito, T. Yoshioka, Adsorption of urea, creatinine, and uric acid onto spherical activated carbon, *Sep. Purif. Technol.* 237 (2020) 116367, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2019.116367>.
- [24] X. Wu, J. Hu, J. Qi, Y. Hou, X. Wei, Graphene-supported ordered mesoporous composites used for environmental remediation: a review, *Sep. Purif. Technol.* 239 (2020) 116511, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2020.116511>.
- [25] M. Sadhu, P. Bhattacharya, M. Vithanage, P.P. Sudhakar, Adsorptive removal of fluoride using biochar – a potential application in drinking water treatment, *Sep. Purif. Technol.* 278 (2021) 119106, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2021.119106>.
- [26] T. Xiong, L. Jia, Q. Li, Y. Zhang, W. Zhu, Efficient removal of uranium by hydroxyapatite modified kaolin aerogel, *Sep. Purif. Technol.* 299 (2022) 121776, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2022.121776>.

- [27] A. Kheradmand, M. Negarestani, S. Kezemi, H. Shayesteh, S. Javanshir, H. Ghiasinejad, E. Jamshidi, Design and preparation magnetic bio-surfactant rhamnolipid-layered double hydroxide nanocomposite as an efficient and recyclable adsorbent for the removal of rifampin from aqueous solution, *Sep. Purif. Technol.* 304 (2023) 122362, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2022.122362>.
- [28] P. Zhang, Y. Chen, Q. Guo, Y. Liu, H. Chong, H. Weng, X. Zhao, Y. Yang, M. Lin, Efficient and selective adsorption of uranium by diamide-pyridine-functionalized hierarchically porous boron nitride, *Sep. Purif. Technol.* 305 (2023) 122538, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2022.122538>.
- [29] M. Kebir, M. Trari, R. Maachi, N. Nasrallah, B. Bellal, A. Amrane, Relevance of a hybrid process coupling adsorption and visible light photocatalysis involving a new hetero-system $\text{CuCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{TiO}_2$ for the removal of hexavalent chromium, *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 3 (2015) 548-559, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2014.12.024>.
- [30] A. Vanaamudan, B. Chavada, P. Padmaja, Adsorption of reactive blue 21 and reactive red 141 from aqueous solutions onto hydrotalcite, *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 4 (2016) 2617–2627, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2016.04.039>.
- [31] P.M. Gore, L. Khurana, R. Dixit, K. Balasubramanian, Keratin-Nylon 6 engineered microbeads for adsorption of Th (IV) ions from liquid effluents, *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 5 (2017) 5655–5667, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2017.10.048>.
- [32] R. Bhatt, P. Padmaja, Spectroscopic signature of branched polyaniline nanotubules decorated with nanospheres as an adsorbent for chromium, *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 6 (2018) 6797–6806, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2018.10.057>.
- [33] H. Mittal, S.M. Alhassan, S.S. Ray, Efficient organic dye removal from wastewater by magnetic carbonaceous adsorbent prepared from corn starch, *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 6 (2018) 7119–7131, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2018.11.010>.

- [34] S. Korde, S. Tandekar, R.M. Jugade, Novel mesoporous chitosan-zirconia-ferrosoferric oxide as magnetic composite for defluoridation of water, *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 8 (2020) 104360, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2020.104360>.
- [35] M.E. Mahmoud, M.M. Saleh, M.M. Zaki, G.M. Nabil, A sustainable nanocomposite for removal of heavy metals from water based on crosslinked sodium alginate with iron oxide waste material from steel industry, *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 8 (2020) 104015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2020.104015>.
- [36] K. Thirumoorthy, S.K. Krishna, Removal of cationic and anionic dyes from aqueous phase by Ball clay – manganese dioxide nanocomposites, *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 8 (2020) 103582, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2019.103582>.
- [37] V. Singh, J. Singh, V. Mishra, Development of a cost-effective, recyclable and viable metal ion doped adsorbent for simultaneous adsorption and reduction of toxic Cr (VI) ions, *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 9 (2021) 105124, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2021.105124>.
- [38] V. Singh, J. Singh, V. Mishra, Sorption kinetics of an eco-friendly and sustainable Cr (VI) ion scavenger in a batch reactor, *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 9 (2021) 105125, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2021.105125>.
- [39] A. Rathi, S. Basu, S. Barman, Structural framework effect of various CeO₂-loaded zeolites on the adsorptive removal of fipronil, *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 9 (2021) 105167, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2021.105167>.
- [40] C.O. Aniagor, E.S. Abdel-Halim, A. Hashem, Evaluation of the aqueous Fe (II) ion sorption capacity of functionalized microcrystalline cellulose, *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 9 (2021) 105703, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2021.105703>.
- [41] T. Shahnaz, V. Sharma, S. Subbiah, S. Narayanasamy, Multivariate optimisation of Cr (VI), Co (III) and Cu (II) adsorption onto nanobentonite incorporated

- nanocellulose/chitosan aerogel using response surface methodology, *J. Water Process Eng.* 36 (2020) 101283, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwpe.2020.101283>.
- [42] T. Shahnaz, V.V. Priyan, S. Pandian, D. Narayanasamy, Use of nanocellulose extracted from grass for adsorption abatement of ciprofloxacin and diclofenac removal with phyto, and fish toxicity studies, *Environ. Pollut.* 268 (2021) 115494, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2020.115494>.
- [43] S. Tasrin, S. Mohamed Madhar Fazil, S. Senthilmurugan, N. Selvaraju, Facile preparation of nanocellulose embedded polypyrrole for dye removal: unary and binary process optimization and seed toxicity, *Int. J. Environ. Sci. Technol.* 18 (2021) 365–378, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13762-020-02814-w>.
- [44] S. Dudek, D. Kołodzyńska, Arsenate removal on the iron oxide ion exchanger modified with neodymium (III) ions, *J. Environ. Manage.* 307 (2022) 114551, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.114551>.
- [45] S. Dudek, D. Kołodzyńska, Arsenic (V) removal on the lanthanum-modified ion exchanger with quaternary ammonium groups based on iron oxide, *J. Mol. Liq.* 347 (2022) 117985, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molliq.2021.117985>.
- [46] S.F.N. Khomeyrani, B. Ghalami-Choobar, M.H.A. Azghandi, M. Foroughi, An enhanced removal of para-nitrophenol (PNP) from water media using CaAl-layered double hydroxide-loaded magnetic g-CN nanocomposite, *J. Water Process Eng.* 46 (2022) 102516, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwpe.2021.102516>.
- [47] Y. Xiao, A.S. Helal, E. Mazario, A. Mayoral, A. Chevillot-Biraud, P. Decorse, R. Losno, F. Maurel, S. Ammar, J.S. Lomas, M. Hémadi, Functionalized maghemite nanoparticles for enhanced adsorption of uranium from simulated wastewater and magnetic harvesting, *Environ. Res.* 216 (2023) 114569, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2022.114569>.

- [48] P. Gore, M. Khraisheh, B. Kandasubramanian, Nanofibers of resorcinol–formaldehyde for effective adsorption of As (III) ions from mimicked effluents, *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 25 (2018) 11729–11745, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-018-1304-z>.
- [49] C. Solisio, S. Al Arni, A. Converti, Adsorption of inorganic mercury from aqueous solutions onto dry biomass of *Chlorella vulgaris*: kinetic and isotherm study, *Environ. Technol.* 40 (2019) 664–672, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09593330.2017.1400114>.
- [50] C. Solisio, E. Spennati, A.A. Casazza, S. Arni, M.S. Alves Palma, A. Converti, Kinetics and isotherms of mercury biosorption by dry biomass of *Arthrospira (Spirulina) platensis*. *Chem. Eng. Technol.* 43 (2020) 240–247, <https://doi.org/10.1002/ceat.201900463>.
- [51] L. Liu, T. Yue, R. Liu, H. Lin, D. Wang, B. Li, Efficient absorptive removal of Cd(II) in aqueous solution by biochar derived from sewage sludge and calcium sulfate, *Bioresour. Technol.* 336 (2021) 125333, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2021.125333>.
- [52] G. Viscusi, E. Lamberti, G. Gorrasi, Design of sodium alginate/soybean extract beads loaded with hemp hurd and halloysite as novel and sustainable systems for methylene blue adsorption, *Polym. Eng. Sci.* 62 (2022) 129–144, <https://doi.org/10.1002/pen.25839>.
- [53] M.R. Parsaeian, S. Dadfarnia, A.M. Haji Shabani, R. Hafezi Moghaddam, Green synthesis of a high capacity magnetic polymer nanocomposite sorbent based on the natural products for removal of reactive black 5, *J. Environ. Anal. Chem.* 102 (2022) 2087–2101, <https://doi.org/10.1080/03067319.2020.1748612>.
- [54] S. Rangabhashiyam, N. Anu, M.S.G. Nandagopal, N. Selvaraju, Relevance of isotherm models in biosorption of pollutants by agricultural byproducts, *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 2 (2014) 398–414, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2014.01.014>.
- [55] R. Saadi, Z. Saadi, R. Fazaeli, N.E. Fard, Monolayer and multilayer adsorption isotherm models for sorption from aqueous media, *Korean J. Chem. Eng.* 32 (2015) 787–799, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11814-015-0053-7>.

- [56] L. Keshavarz, M.R. Ghaani, J.D. MacElroy, N.J. English, 2021. A comprehensive review on the application of aerogels in CO₂-adsorption: materials and characterization, *Chem. Eng. J.* 412 (2021) 128604, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2021.128604>.
- [57] M.M. Majd, V. Kordzadeh-Kermani, V. Ghalandari, A. Askari, M. Sillanpää, Adsorption isotherm models: a comprehensive and systematic review (2010–2020), *Sci. Total Environ.* 812 (2022) 151334, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.151334>.
- [58] A. Gürses, S. Karaca, C. Doğar, R. Bayrak, M. Açıkyıldız, M. Yalçın, Determination of adsorptive properties of clay/water system: methylene blue sorption, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 269 (2004) 310–314, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcis.2003.09.004>.
- [59] G.d.V. Brião, M.G.C. da Silva, M.G.A. Vieira, K.H. Chu, Correlation of type II adsorption isotherms of water contaminants using modified BET equations, *Colloid Interface Sci. Commun.* 46 (2022) 100557, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colcom.2021.100557>.
- [60] M. Yılmaz, M.A. Hashim, K.H. Chu, Description of sigmoid adsorption isotherms of water pollutants by the Aranovich–Donohue equation, *Sep. Sci. Technol.* 57 (2022) 2908–2915, <https://doi.org/10.1080/01496395.2022.2097093>.
- [61] L.D. Fiorentin, D.E.G. Trigueros, A.N. Módenes, F.R. Espinoza-Quiñones, N.C. Pereira, S.T.D. Barros, O.A.A. Santos, Biosorption of reactive blue 5G dye onto drying orange bagasse in batch system: kinetic and equilibrium modeling, *Chem. Eng. J.* 163 (2010) 68–77, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2010.07.043>.
- [62] B. Lan, Y. Wang, X. Wang, X. Zhou, Y. Kang, L. Li, Aqueous arsenic (As) and antimony (Sb) removal by potassium ferrate, *Chem. Eng. J.* 292 (2016) 389–397, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2016.02.019>.

- [63] M. Otero, M. Zabkova, A.E. Rodrigues, Adsorptive purification of phenol wastewaters: experimental basis and operation of a parametric pumping unit, *Chem. Eng. J.* 110 (2005) 101-111, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2005.02.033>.
- [64] S. Hamidouche, O. Bouras, F. Zermane, B. Cheknane, M. Houari, J. Debord, M. Harel, J.C. Bollinger, M. Baudu, Simultaneous sorption of 4-nitrophenol and 2-nitrophenol on a hybrid geocomposite based on surfactant-modified pillared-clay and activated carbon, *Chem. Eng. J.* 279 (2015) 964–972, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2015.05.012>.

Supplementary Material

The Halsey isotherm for water contaminant adsorption is fake

Khim Hoong Chu ^{a,*}, Hadis Bashiri ^b, Mohd Ali Hashim ^a,

Mohd Yunus Abd Shukor ^c, Jean-Claude Bollinger ^d

^a Department of Chemical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, University of Malaya, Kuala Lumpur 50603, Malaysia

^b Department of Physical Chemistry, Faculty of Chemistry, University of Kashan, Kashan, Iran

^c Department of Biochemistry, Faculty of Biotechnology and Biomolecular Sciences, Universiti Putra Malaysia, Agriculture Innovation Life, Serdang 43400, Selangor, Malaysia

^d Université de Limoges, Laboratoire E2Lim, Faculté des Sciences & Techniques, 87060 Limoges, France

* Corresponding author.

Email address: khimchu@gmail.com (K.H. Chu)

Contents

- 1. The fake Halsey isotherm**
- 2. Misapplication of the fake Halsey isotherm: daidzein adsorption by nanozeolite beta**
- 3. Misapplication of the fake Halsey isotherm: Ni(II) adsorption by modified biochar**

1. The fake Halsey isotherm

The fake Halsey isotherm, given by Eq. (S1), is a linear expression with two fitting parameters, n and k , which can be determined by means of linear regression. It can be expressed in the form of Eq. (S2), which is nonlinear in the two fitting parameters. Although Eq. (S1) is a relatively simple expression, several studies have reported erroneous estimates for n and k .

$$\ln(q) = \frac{1}{n} \ln(k) - \frac{1}{n} \ln(c) \quad (\text{S1})$$

$$q = \left(\frac{k}{c} \right)^{1/n} \quad (\text{S2})$$

2. Misapplication of the fake Halsey isotherm: daidzein adsorption by nanozeolite beta

A 2018 paper [S1] describes the adsorption of the phytoestrogen daidzein by a nanozeolite beta adsorbent. The experimental isotherm was correlated using seven isotherm models, including the fake Halsey isotherm given by Eq. (S1). The best-fit Halsey parameters (n and k) reported in the original study [S1] are presented in Table S1, column 2. Fig. S1A shows the fake Halsey isotherm fit of this work; the resulting parameter estimates are given in Table S1, column 3. As seen in Table S1, the numerical value of our estimate for n is in good agreement with the reported value. However, our n estimate is a negative value whereas the reported n is a positive number. Because n is used in the calculation of k , it is not surprising to see that our estimate for k differs significantly from the reported k value.

The two sets of parameter estimates are used in Eq. (S2) to plot the q versus c curves shown in Figs. S1B and S1C. As can be seen in Fig. S1B, the calculated curve based on the parameter estimates of the original study deviates significantly from the hyperbolic data trend. In contrast, the hyperbolic data trend is well tracked by the calculated curve based on the parameter estimates of this work, as can be seen in Fig. S1C. It is evident that the parameter estimates reported in the original study are faulty. This error (positive sign for n) is rather common; additional examples can be found in the literature of water contaminant adsorption.

Table S1. Parameter estimates obtained by fitting the fake Halsey isotherm [Eq. (S1)] to daidzein adsorption data [S1].

Parameter	Original study [S1]	Present study
n	1.485	-1.45
k (mg L ⁻¹)(mg g ⁻¹) ^{n}	43.797	0.025

Fig. S1. (A) Linear fit of the fake Halsey isotherm [Eq. (S1)] to daidzein adsorption data [S1]. (B) Comparison of daidzein adsorption data and q versus c curve calculated from Eq. (S2) using the erroneous linear regression-generated parameters of the original study [S1]. (C) Comparison of daidzein adsorption data and q versus c curve calculated from Eq. (S2) using the correct linear regression-generated parameters of this work.

3. Misapplication of the fake Halsey isotherm: Ni(II) adsorption by modified biochar

A very recent article reports the adsorption of three toxic metals [Pb(II), Cd(II), and Ni(II)] by several modified biochar materials [S2]. Four isotherm models, including the fake Halsey isotherm [Eq. (S1)], were used to correlate the experimental data. The selected data set describes Ni(II) adsorption on a modified biochar adsorbent (designated as CMC@MBC3 in the original study). Fig. S2A shows the fit of Eq. (S1) to the experimental data by means of linear regression, while Table S2 gives the resulting parameter estimates (column 3).

Table S2. Parameter estimates obtained by fitting the fake Halsey isotherm [Eq. (S1)] to Ni(II) adsorption data [S2].

Parameter	Original study [S1]	Present study
n	0.46	-2.04
k (mg L ⁻¹)(mg g ⁻¹) ^{n}	0.62	0.0094

Fig. S2. (A) Linear fit of the fake Halsey isotherm [Eq. (S1)] to Ni(II) adsorption data [S2]. (B) Comparison of Ni(II) adsorption data and q versus c curve calculated from Eq. (S2) using the erroneous linear regression-generated parameters of the original study [S2]. (C) Comparison of Ni(II) adsorption data and q versus c curve calculated from Eq. (S2) using the correct linear regression-generated parameters of this work.

For comparison with our results, the parameter estimates reported in the original study [S2] are shown in Table S2, column 2. Table S2 shows that the reported parameter estimates differ significantly from our estimates. The discrepancy is due to sloppy treatment of the modeling results in the original study. The value of n reported by Zhang et al. [S2] is in fact the slope of the linear fit. From Eq. (S1), we see that the slope is equal to $-1/n$. So, with slope = 0.46, it follows that $n = -1/0.46 = -2.17$, which agrees with our estimate of -2.04 for n .

Figs. S2B and S2C plot the q versus c curves calculated from Eq. (S2) using the parameter estimates reported by Zhang et al. [S2] and our parameter estimates. We immediately notice that their parameter estimates are nonsensical because the calculated curve shown in Fig. S2B bears little resemblance to the experimental Ni(II) isotherm, which is hyperbolic in shape. To show the experimental data in Fig. S2B, the scales of the two axes need to be changed. The overall hyperbolic shape of the experimental isotherm is well tracked by the curve calculated using our parameter estimates, as can be seen in Fig. S2C. A plot of q versus c can be used to verify linear regression-generated parameter estimates, as was done in Figs. S2B and S2C. It has been our experience that this safeguard has been largely overlooked by users of linearized isotherm models.

References

- [S1] N. Goyal, V.K. Bulasara, S. Barman, S., Removal of emerging contaminants daidzein and coumestrol from water by nanozeolite beta modified with tetrasubstituted ammonium cation, *J. Hazard. Mater.* 344 (2018) 417–430, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2017.10.051>.
- [S2] H. Zhang, H. Yang, J. Shao, Y. Chen, S. Zhang, H. Chen, Multifunctional carboxymethyl cellulose sodium encapsulated phosphorus-enriched biochar composites: multistage adsorption of heavy metals and controllable release of soil fertilization, *Chem. Eng. J.* 453 (2023) 139809, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2022.139809>.